

TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS JUNIOR COURSES OF LAW FACULTIES

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Ravshanova Dilshoda

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Abstract: *At University law faculties, a foreign language is provided for 1 and 2 years of study for 2 hours a week. Group occupancy is the same as for all specialties (10-12 people). Given the relentless growth in the importance of foreign language proficiency in the legal profession, these learning conditions can be described as extremely difficult. Even the growing importance of the subject for professional training has not yet affected the improvement of these conditions. These circumstances complicate the solution of the two main issues that have always been faced by methodologists who study the problems of methods of teaching foreign languages at non-linguistic faculties in non-linguistic universities. The following article provides a detailed analysis of these issues.*

Keywords: *law, language, profession, problem, learning.*

INTRODUCTION

The first of these problems is the correlation and correlation of General language training with special, that is, professionally directed training. What should be their specific weight in comparison with each other, whether there should be a strict division between these two components at all, and if so, when should special professionally oriented training begin.

The second problem is the ratio of reading and speaking instruction in nonlanguage faculties. As you know, for many decades, the main goal of teaching foreign languages at a non-linguistic faculty was considered to be teaching reading texts in the specialty, and only in the last decades, oral speech as a learning goal is gradually gaining territory in a non-linguistic University. Taking into account that, on the one hand, the learning conditions have not improved, and on the other hand, now no one doubts the orientation of teaching a foreign language as a communication both in the General sphere of activity and in the professional sphere, and no one denies the need to teach students not only reading, but also oral speech, the question arises whether it is possible to achieve the intended goals in these conditions of training.

METHODOLOGY

There are a number of factors that to some extent compensate for the negative impact of what Michael West would call "Teaching English in difficult circumstances". These factors are as follows: first, despite the critical attitude to school teaching of foreign languages, it is necessary to recognize that the level of

readiness of graduates entering law faculties is much higher today than it was when the main problems of teaching foreign languages at non - language faculties were raised. The data on the readiness of first-year students to understand authentic texts in law, which we have received in repeated checks over the past years, is generally very encouraging. Secondly, a student who has entered the faculty of law has a high motivation to learn a foreign language. moreover, about % of students realize that a career as a lawyer without knowledge of foreign languages, especially English, is less promising. And this external motivation is of serious importance. The third is undoubtedly the existing difference between non-linguistic specialties in terms of the degree of ease of reading special texts. This difference affects, first of all, the degree of proximity (or remoteness) of special terms and General vocabulary; the level of pre-university students' awareness of the chosen specialty and its basic concepts is essential. In this respect, law is a relatively "profitable" specialty. Legal characters, legal stories, and legal designations are largely internationalized, and the percentage of words and phrases that are both terms and units of a common language is very high. Law undoubtedly belongs to those Sciences whose English terminology is complex, first of all, because of its ambiguity, and not because of isolation from the General vocabulary. the fourth important factor is the proximity of law to the life of the common man. "Right and law stand in the middle of life." They regulate it, and hence the ease of saturation of General language training with elements of a legal specialty, permeating almost any household or cultural topic with elements of jurisprudence. the fifth factor is the role that law plays in the life of the country of the language being studied. Let's start with the fact that achievements in law, their practical implementation are the primary national pride of English speaking countries. The future lawyer either already knows or will be convinced that England is not only the birthplace of the rule of law, it is a country where law and respect for law are both an integral and everyday element of everyone's life. In this respect, the United States is not far behind its "mother Country". The complex influence of these factors is an objective prerequisite for the assumption that with an adequate and, at the same time, averaged method, it is possible to postulate reading authentic literature in the specialty and teaching oral speech on a series of professional topics, starting from the first year.

RESULTS

Due to the limitation of studying a foreign language course at the Faculty of Law for only 2 years, the problem of maximum movement of the beginning of reading texts in the specialty and learning oral communication on professional topics by the beginning of the first year becomes extremely important. At the same time, instead of contrasting General and special training, their interpenetration is an integral task. In view of the above, the prospects for a positive solution to the problems put forward above have a solid Foundation. Therefore, the dependence on an adequate methodology for teaching foreign languages at law schools is crucial. The methodological literature still lacks special research on teaching English in Junior

years, which is the rationale for the relevance of choosing the topic of our dissertation. The above-mentioned factors that favor teaching English at the Junior courses of law faculties give grounds to formulate the research hypothesis as follows: when teaching a foreign language at law faculties, General language and specific professional language training from the first days of study at the University should be carried out in a complex, which applies to all skills and abilities. The content of training should involve reading authentic texts from the very beginning and using them as a means of teaching oral speech. In the field of development of oral and speech skills, those that allow professional saturation with elements of jurisprudence should be selected from the topics of oral speech. Along with this, professional - oriented oral-speech texts should take an increasingly significant place for teaching students oral - speech communication in special legal scenarios. Element of law of all English language learning needs to be systematic and to be chosen in such a way that it was presented the main legal science (criminal law, international law, civil law, etc.) There is reason to believe that the implementation of this training ensures sufficient cross-cultural training of a legal nature. To form and test this hypothesis, it was necessary to solve the following tasks: to provide a theoretical basis for professionally oriented training in a foreign language; to analyze the state of English language training for Junior law students; to analyze textbooks, manuals, and curricula on legal specialty; to determine the content of professionally oriented English language training for Junior law students; to develop a system of tasks for the formation of communication skills of indirect and direct business communication and to test its effectiveness in the course of experienced training. To solve these tasks, the following research methods were used: study and analysis of literature in the field of methods of teaching English, linguistics, psycholinguistics, lingua-didactics, psychology; analysis of educational and methodological literature, programs for law students; linguistic analysis of authentic texts of legal orientation; questionnaires of students to determine their needs in learning a foreign language; individual conversations with students and teachers of General and special disciplines; experimental training. Scientific novelty of the research: to determine the content of training, which included authentic texts, as well as professionally-oriented scenario of business communication taking into account cultural differences; developed the technique of indirect and direct professional business communication, theoretically grounded professionally - oriented English language training second year students of legal specialization; selected skills that are important for orientation in the structure of authentic texts for different purposes for quick understanding of these texts, as well as the ability to navigate the pragmatic setting of the text, to learn lexico-grammatical means of realization of pragmatic aspect of the content, understand the information of the text.

CONCLUSION

Based on the fact that experiential learning is a science performed an experiment based on studying of a condition and dynamics of the phenomenon, we have reason to believe: professionally-oriented training of Junior students of law faculties equips them with the skills to work independently with authentic texts; working with a variety of types of authentic texts legal orientation promotes the development of skills of orientation in the structure and using it as a means of understanding the information; work with legal terminology based on the conceptual genre approach allows forming paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations of terminology, develops the language and contextual guess, contributes to the accumulation of individual dictionary of each student; significantly improved speaking students; they have successfully mastered the scripts of professionally-oriented communication, their speech became more directed, emotional, situational; increased rate of speech, which is important for communication. The conducted experimental training confirmed the expediency of the proposed research methodology and its effectiveness.

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